

Observations of Ambient Noises Induced by the Internal Solitary Waves on the Continental Slope of the Northern South China Sea

Ambient Noises by ISW in SCS

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Abstract—The “Sand Dunes” moored array in the upper slope of the northern South China Sea provided an unprecedented look at internal solitary wave (ISW) arrival patterns and transformations under shoaling as they propagate northwestward passed the sand dunes. The data sets also shown the underwater ambient noise induced by the ISW. The mode-1 depression ISW could generate the surface wave breaking in the convergence zone and produce ocean noises. These ocean noises in high sonic bands would be enhanced in the convergence zone and reduced in the divergence zone due to rough and smooth sea surface conditions, respectively. Besides, the strong horizontal currents induced by internal solitary waves would produce self-noise in the infra and low sonic bands. In addition, sometime, the acoustic data also show the marine mammal sounds behind the ISW. This result might due to the marine mammals follow the ISWs to prey on fish and squid.

Keywords—underwater ambient noise, internal solitary wave

I. INTRODUCTION

The internal solitary wave (ISW) is a localized internal gravity wave that occurs in a stratified ocean. Most observed internal solitary waves can be categorized as mode-1 waves. A mode-1 internal solitary wave displaces isotherms downward in deep water, but upward when the upper layer becomes thicker than the lower layer. The former type is known as a depression wave, and the latter, an elevation wave. The ISW not only induces the vertical motion, density perturbations, and nutrient pumping, but also changes the underwater ambient noise.

Several large field experiments over the last decade have documented the existence of very large ISWs in the northeastern South China Sea [1]. The internal tide is generated by the flux of the barotropic tide over two ridges in the Luzon Strait [2]. The tide subsequently propagates WNW

across the deep basin where it steepens under the influence of nonlinearity and rotation, finally breaking and spawning the largest ISW in the world [3]. As these mode-1 depression waves shoal up the continental slope, they interact with the bottom, grow more, split into packets, form elevation waves and higher-mode waves, and ultimately dissipate somewhere in shallow water over the continental shelf. In addition, the ISW shoal on continental slope and force nutrients and plankton into upper-ocean [4].

The ISW generated the surface wave breaking in the convergence zone and it would produce ocean noises and its associated sea surface signatures can be imaged by radars [5], [6]. In addition, the ISW would change the thermal structure as well as the sound-speed fluctuations. Therefore, the aspects of underwater acoustic propagation would be modified by the internal solitary waves [7]-[9].

Fig. 1. A composite of 38 kHz and 120 kHz echogram for depth zones below and above 200 m, respectively, showing the 125 m amplitude ISW and 5-16 m amplitude sand dunes along a single 45 km track. (From [1]).

Fig. 2. The echogram of 38 kHz showing the 125 m amplitude ISW packet passed the sand dunes.

On the upper continental slope of the northern South China Sea, the very large subaqueous sand dunes (Fig. 1) were discovered by Reeder et al. [10]. The Fig. 2 shows an example of ISWs over the sand dunes on the continental slope of the northern South China Sea. This ISW packet was definitely hitting the bottom and the spatial scale of the dunes was much

smaller than the ISW. The suspended sediment over the dune field seems to track the dunes suggesting the vertical velocity was following the dunes (or vice versa). The sand dunes not only influenced the energy dissipation of ISW, but also re-suspended the sediment. This mechanism also would induced the underwater ambient noise. In this paper, we will study the impact of ISW on underwater ambient noises in the sand dunes area on the upper continental slope of the northern South China Sea. This paper is organized as follows. Section II gives a general description of the field works. Observed results are presented in Section III. Finally, Section IV provides a discussion.

II. OBSERVATION

The Taiwan-US collaborative field study designed to characterize these sand dunes, the associated physical processes and the associated acoustic scattering physics. These sand dunes are compelling for a number of scientific and operational reasons, including the expected significant impact on ecology and sonar. The temporal and spatial scales and the distribution of these sand dunes were completely unknown prior to this study, as well as the potential impact on sound transmission, in terms of both phenomenology and statistics.

Ten moorings were deployed in the sand dunes area on the upper continental slope of the northern South China Sea (Fig. 3) from the R/V Ocean Researcher I (OR1) conducted from May 31-June 5, 2014. The all of moorings were recovery from the R/V Ocean Researcher V (OR5) conducted from June 10-21, 2014.

The mooring array included 4 environmental moorings, one sound source mooring, one vertical line array (VLA) mooring, and 4 serval hydrophone recorder unit (SHRU) moorings. Each environmental mooring equipped serval self-contained Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) and thermistor chins. In order to avoid the cable strumming noise, we used the Kevlar rope with hairy fairing for the SHRU mooring lines. Fig. 4 is the moorings array diagram.

Fig. 3. Moorings array were deployed in the sand dunes area on the upper continental slope of northern South China Sea. The red dots represent the environmental, sound source, and VLA moorings. The yellow triangles represent the SHRU moorings.

Fig. 4. The schematic drawings of the 10 moorings.

III. RESULTS

Fig. 5 is a Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) image captured at 03:10 GMT on 17 June 2014. Signals revealed several ISW packets around moorings array. According to the curvature of the leading wave and subsequent waves, these wave packets were primarily propagating northwestward. Fig. 6 shows temperature contour plots for CPO environmental mooring as a function of depth and time from 12:00 GMT, 16 June to 12:00 GMT, 17 June, 2005. Two mode-1 depression ISW packets around 04:00 and 06:00 GMT 17 June 2014.

Fig. 7 shows time-depth contours of acoustic data for YS2 SHRU mooring on June 17, 2014. Two peaks of acoustic data were around 03:30 GMT and 06:00 GMT. The maximum of emergence time in high and low sonic hands were not consistent. The acoustic data of low sonic bands were about a couple of minutes lagged behind the high sonic bands in each peak. These two peaks would be related to the two mode-1 depression ISWs.

Fig. 5. MODIS (bands 1, 3, and 4) 250-m resolution visible image near moorings array acquired on 21 June 2014 at 03:10 GMT. The red dots represent the moorings location.

Fig. 6. Color contours of isotherm depth for CPO mooring from 12:00 GMT, 16 June to 12:00 GMT 17 June, 2014.

Fig. 7. From top to bottom panels show the color contour plots of the acoustic power spectral density by linear and log scales in depth, respectively, on June 14, 2014.

IV. DISCUSSION

The primary of observation results shown the underwater ambient noise in high sonic bands were enhanced and reduced in the front and rear portions of ISW, respectively. These results were related to the mode-1 depression ISW would be induced the rough and smooth sea surface conditions in the front and rear portions of ISW, respectively. Besides, the ambient noise in the infra and low sonic bands would be enhanced in the central of ISW. This phenomenon affected by the strong current speed induced by the ISW. The noises at infra and low sonic bands were pseudo-noise resulting from the presence of the hydrophone and its supporting structure in a current. This self-noise is also called the "flow-noise".

In addition, sometime, the acoustic data also show the marine mammal sounds behind the ISW. This result might due to the upwelling in the rear portion of mode-1 depression ISW could indeed entrain small fishes and squids. The whales could follow the ISW to prey on fish and squid [11].

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